

LESSONS FROM NARRATIVES OF BLAAN LEARNERS

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Lessons from Narratives of Blaan Learners

Elbert G. Pogado,* Lilibeth R. Bagtas

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This descriptive phenomenology study aimed to glean insights from the narratives of Blaan learners, an indigenous community residing in Mindanao. Specifically, the study sought to capture the lived experiences and perspectives of Blaan learners, shedding light on their unique challenges and resilience. Five (5) Blaan learners from Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School were purposively sampled for in-depth interviews. The findings revealed that Blaan learners often traverse dangerous routes to school, assume independence at a young age, and come from large families. These experiences underscore the resilience of Blaan learners amidst adversity. However, they also highlight the significant challenges they face in accessing education and navigating their daily lives. In light of these findings, targeted interventions are recommended to support the educational journey and well-being of Blaan learners. Suggestions include the creation of safe road designs along school routes by the Local Government Unit (LGU), strengthening law enforcement within school zones, equipping learners with safety skills, and implementing weekly feeding programs for Blaan learners and other Indigenous youth. Additionally, initiatives such as counselling sessions addressing early marriage and parental separation among Blaan youth may be beneficial. This study emphasized the importance of understanding the unique experiences of indigenous communities like the Blaan, and advocates for proactive measures to address their specific needs and challenges.

Keywords: *indigenous people, Blaan, narratives*

Introduction

The Blaan tribe is one of the indigenous groups that inhabited the hills of Southern Mindanao. I was assigned to a school located in Lanao Kapanglao where the majority of the community is Blaan. As an educator, I have seen the situations of the Blaan learners and the challenges they had to face every day when going to school. Most of them go to school with no allowances and have to walk long distances to reach school. When the area was affected by flood and storm, the learners wade through the flood water. Lack of educational resources and materials for the Blaan learners was also one of the common problems.

Some of the Blaan learners do not have access to the same quality of education that other children have had access to (Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development, 2017). Despite this, there are only a few studies conducted about the lived experiences of Blaan learners.

Although there was an abundance of inquiry in the field of Indigenous education, much of it continued to be undertaken by predominantly non-Indigenous academics and without significant records that privileged the voices and lived experiences of Indigenous People (Shay, 2016). I found children at very young ages on busy streets, working to earn a living and accommodating the needs of their respective families.

The Philippine 1987 Constitution Article 14 stated that the State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all (Atienza, 2019). But even though the duty of the country was to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality basic education, Blaan learners still face the mentioned challenges each day—financial scarcity, difficulty in transportation to school, and different cultural norms and beliefs.

Due to the insignificant records and lack of privilege to voice out their experiences, I aimed to conduct a study and understand lessons from the narratives of Blaan learners and focus on the challenges they encounter in their daily life. Instead of believing the myths that surround their social group, I learned their adversities from their narratives that may create a heightened awareness of the background of the Blaan learners as well as the whole Indigenous People community and reduce the society's misconceptions about them. Despite the abundance of inquiry in the field of Indigenous education, the topic of Indigenous education can be interdisciplinary and complex to understand. As an educator, I hope that this study can also contribute much knowledge especially now that many classes in schools are culturally diverse.

Research Questions

I believe that concerns associated with indigenous groups are equally as significant as other societal problems. Learning the adversities of the younger generation may help eliminate the negative connotations of Indigenous groups. Hence, in this study, I sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the Blaan learners?
2. What lessons can be grounded on the experiences of the learners?

Literature Review

Theoretical Lens

This study was anchored on Jerome Bruner's Narrative Construction of Reality. According to Bruner (1991), narrative was a conventional form, transmitted culturally and constrained by each individual's level of mastery and by his conglomerate of prosthetic devices, colleagues, and mentors. Unlike the constructions generated by logical and scientific procedures which could be weeded out by falsification, narrative constructions could only achieve verisimilitude. To help me understand the experiences of the Blaan learners, I used a narrative construction analysis as the theoretical lens of the study.

Furthermore, through the experience of learning, the learner selected and transformed information, constructed hypotheses, and made decisions, relying on a cognitive structure to do so (Columbia Theological Seminary, 2014). Learning was an active process in which learners constructed new ideas or concepts based upon their current and past knowledge, while the cognitive structures helped create meaning and organization to experiences and allowed the learner to go beyond the information given by the teacher.

I followed Hein (1991) as theoretical model in believing that if I accepted narrative construction theory (which means I was willing to follow in the path of Dewey, Piaget, and Vigotsky among others), then I had to give up Platonic and all subsequent realistic views of epistemology. I had to recognize that there was no such thing as knowledge "out there" independent of the knower, but only knowledge we constructed for ourselves as we learn.

There are other various definitions of narrative construction, however, the most essential and closely related to understanding of this study was that gaining new knowledge was based on previous experiences. Mcleod (2019) stated that each individual learner had a distinctive point of view, based on existing knowledge and values. Therefore, the knowledge and lessons gathered from the narratives of the Blaan learners came from my experiences and my distinctive point of view was based on my own constructed knowledge.

The theoretical framework of narrative construction, for that reason, was relevant to generate lessons from the narratives of the Blaan learners.

Lived Experiences of the Blaan People

According to Frechette, Bitzas, Aubry, Kilpatrick, and Lavoie-Tremblay (2020), a lived experience was not only something that was experienced, it was something being experienced that made a special impression and gave it lasting importance. It is a personal knowledge gained through direct experience. An account of lived experience was incomplete if it remained purely descriptive; it must contain an interpretation of significance for the person. Consequently, narrative and argumentation have historically been seen as opposites, rooted in Aristotle's differentiation between logic and emotion. This division separates the realm of reason and evidence from that of storytelling and emotional engagement. However, it is important to note that narrative and argumentation are not mutually exclusive but can be effectively combined in communication. While argumentation relies on logic and evidence to persuade, narrative uses storytelling and emotions to convey messages and connect with audiences. Today, there is an increasing recognition of the value of narratives in various fields, as they have the power to engage and shape perspectives alongside logical arguments. Ultimately, narrative and argumentation can work together to create persuasive and impactful communication (Herrick, 1997 cited by Bilandzic & Buselle, 2017)

Indigenous people were culturally distinct societies and communities. The land on which they lived and the natural resources on which they depended were inextricably linked to their identities, cultures, livelihoods, as well as their physical and spiritual well-being (World Bank Group, 2019).

The question of inequality and psychic trauma was most visible in relation to indigenous peoples and the dehumanizing colonization of their countries. There was an exceptionally limited body of knowledge on indigenous farmworkers and distress. In Australia, for example, indigenous peoples were the most at risk of suicide; however, little was known about indigenous farmers and farmworkers in relation to suicide and biosocial bodily well-being (Shaw, 2020).

According to Beittle (2000) cited by Kuper, Omura, Plaice, Ramos, Robins, and Suzman (2013), culture had become a common euphemism for a race. Similarly, in the rhetoric of the indigenous people's movement, the terms native and indigenous were often euphemisms for what used to be termed primitive.

Meanwhile, in the southern part of the Philippines, indigenous tribes were mostly found in Mindanao and Western Visayas. In Mindanao, these existing Non-Muslim indigenous groups were collectively known as the Lumad – a Cebuano term which means 'native' or 'indigenous' but were known today as 'ethnic tribes of Mindanao'. The ethnic tribes of Mindanao comprised about 13 ethnic groups which were the Blaan, Bukidnon, Higaonon, Mamanwa, Mandaya, Manobo, Mansaka, Sangir, Subanen, Tagabawa, Tagakaulo, Tasaday, and T'boli. Their tribe was generally known for tribal music produced by musical instruments they created (Valdeavilla, 2018).

Despite the abundance of natural resources around them, the indigenous peoples (IPs) in the Philippines, like their global counterparts, were ranked among the poorest and most disadvantaged sectors. They were deprived of rights and opportunities to develop capacities

to cope with the fast-changing social, economic, and political environment (International Labour Organization, 2017).

Moreover, Minority Rights Group International (2020) stated that the Indigenous People had some of the lowest educational levels in the Philippines, in accessing schooling. Part of the problem was the entrenched discrimination towards indigenous youths within the centrally managed school system, which often treated them as outsiders and second-class citizens. The time and cost of traveling long distances to reach public schools also place insurmountable burdens on many Lumad families. Indigenous activists in the southern Philippines insisted that the right to free and culturally tailored education was fundamental to defending Indigenous heritage and rights, which were often intimately tied to the protection of ancestral lands and resources.

The lack of budget had resulted in generally poorer living conditions and a higher incidence of poverty in regions where indigenous peoples were found or concentrated. This was seen, for instance, in the fact that Mindanao, where sixty-one percent (61%) of indigenous peoples live, contributed thirty-one percent (31%) of the total poverty incidence in the country and had the highest poverty and subsistence incidence among major island groups in the country (Plant, 2013).

A more substantial implementation of the law was still sought, as the indigenous peoples of the Philippines continue to live in geographically isolated areas with a lack of access to basic social services and few opportunities for widespread economic activities, education, or political participation (International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs, 2019).

Consequently, in a study conducted by Martin, Fernandes, Taylor, Crow, Headland, Shaw, and Zammit (2019) on the lived experience of the Aboriginal People in Australia, they had found out that informants experienced a disconnection from kin and country, serious risk to personal safety, homelessness, and problematic health. Moreover, the study highlighted the narratives of the informants on how they endured the impact of colonization, dispossession, and racism. Meanwhile, research by Du (2017) revealed that relevant publications about Indigenous People fluctuated almost every year, with the highest number of publications in 2007. International Information and Library Review was the most prolific journal publishing a wide range of articles in the area and Laurel Evelyn Dyson from Australia was the most productive author. However, among these publications, only nine percent (9%) had reported explicitly that they were financially supported.

After learning about the lived experience of Indigenous people and their struggle for identity and recognition, the following topic tackled the perspectives of the non-Indigenous people and their actions toward the Indigenous communities.

Perspectives and Actions toward the Blaan Community

According to Putt (2013), Blaan populations were dispersed and diverse, and although only one-quarter of the Blaan population lived in remote and very remote communities, much of the research on health and social issues had been undertaken in remote communities. Based on extensive experience in public health research, Putt (2013) also made a series of suggestions for engaging with Indigenous communities in an urban context, including approaching a peak body relevant to the research topic for advice on who to consult, formalizing the collaborative relationship through a memorandum of understanding, and ensuring appropriate acknowledgments of contributions. From the viewpoint of someone who is not Indigenous, engaging in the research process may present challenges that require adaptability, openness to change, and ongoing negotiation. It may involve relinquishing control and adopting a new perspective or way of thinking (Skille, 2021).

According to Asian Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Network (2014), the Philippines is one of the first nations in Asia to have approved a law recognizing the rights and development needs of indigenous peoples (IPs). Enacted in 1997, the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA) commands the State to uphold and protect the rights of IPs to their ancestral domain, self-governance, social justice, and cultural integrity. The IPRA law has also authorized the creation of the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) to promote the interests of IPs "with due regard to their beliefs, customs, traditions, and institutions". This specific attention to the needs of the IPs draws from the 1987 Philippine Constitution's provision to "recognize, respect, and protect the rights of indigenous cultural communities to preserve and develop their cultures, traditions, and institutions" (Cornelio & Castro, 2016).

Although the IPRA was passed in 1997, the development of policies catering to indigenous education was considerably slow and inevitably confined to changes in national administration. It was not until 2004, for example, when the Department of Education released an executive order giving permits to operate schools for IPs (Delfin, 2012).

In addition, international development organizations have also contributed to addressing the needs for indigenous education in the Philippines. Often, having partnerships with the State is necessary for international organizations to implement their programs. UNESCO, for example, has recognized the relocations among indigenous communities due to natural calamities and military conflicts. It has, therefore, partnered with various State agencies and NGOs to design Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) and Alternative Learning System (ALS) for emergency education in Mindanao (Azoulay, 2018). AusAID, too, had recently offered its resources to the Philippines' Response to Indigenous Peoples' and Muslim Education Program (PRIME) of the Department of Education. Providing funds and technical assistance, AusAID has aimed to increase the "demand for educational services" in indigenous communities and support the systems and mechanisms of the Department of Education in providing quality indigenous education (AusAID, 2012).

Furthermore, the Copenhagen-based International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs noted that the Philippine government approved the Certificates of Ancestral Domain Title (CADT), which "now help indigenous communities to assert control over their territories

and they create the incentives to sustainably manage and protect their forest and other natural resources.” Indeed, in some indigenous communities, such as the Subanen, indigenous leaders were able to participate “in local government” as well as “titling of ancestral domains” as “part of the overall goal of strengthening self-governance of ancestral domains” (International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs, 2019).

However, there are other issues that have remained unresolved. Reports by various human rights organizations show human rights violations relating to mining operations in ancestral lands, while other human rights of indigenous peoples continue to be violated in general (Amnesty International, 2019).

According to Marahon, Demacota, Espirito, and Obregon (2012) in their study about youth Indigenous People in Davao del Sur, discrimination still exists to this day. These discriminations are commonly expressed verbally, and commonly because of having generalized beliefs or stereotype beliefs and being uneducated. Moreover, it was reported that the indigenous youth in the said community has low educational attainment due to financial incapacity and having fears of being discriminated against by other students in school, while few claimed that they had gone to school but were still said to experience discrimination expressed subtly.

In connection to this, the indigenous students also suffered severe marginalization. They were judged based on their accent and language, were often called demeaning names, and negative judgments that resulted in unjustified negative behavior towards a group or its members (Galindo, Reginio, Ligid, Sancon, and Advincula, 2018). Myers (2020), in the context of Social Psychology, explained that this marginalization and prejudice towards a certain group were due to social inequalities.

Nevertheless, as added by Espesor (2014), despite numerous natural disasters that constantly confronted the upland communities, the Blaans had learned various survival mechanisms and most of which were taught by their ancestors. During times of food scarcity brought about by drought, community members had reduced to eating klot or poisonous wild yam to stave off hunger.

According to Ancheta, Pelovello, Romero, Reden, Gannaban, and Tindowen (2017), indigenous people are firm in finding ways that they will live. Most of the elders did not enter or finish school but that did not hinder them to be good breadwinners of their respective families. They utilize their environment efficiently whether it be the mountains or sea around them. They are seen to be industrious people who will not waste time inside their houses, instead, they are firm in finding means to survive every single day. In their account, some of them are helpers and caretakers in business establishments in cities while others continue to search the seas and the forests for whatever it may give them.

Students were the hope of our generation and their opinions greatly matter as they would become leaders someday. However, they were still children and their psychological health was important.

Common Struggles of Learners at School

Learners updated the concept of a student, potentially distancing the term from the characteristics and connotations traditionally associated with the word student (The Glossary of Education Reform, 2014). It was difficult to plan a curriculum that grabs the attention of young learners, challenging to think of assessment as a mentor rather than a judge of learning, demanding to plan instruction that accounts for learners’ needs, and daunting to guide a classroom that was premised on the need for flexibility (Tomlinson, 2014).

As stated by Pinter (2017), adult learners could rely on a number of useful resources when they learn a new language. They could analyze language in an abstract way. This ability would allow them to compare patterns and linguistic forms that were similar or different in their mother tongue and in the other language.

Moreover, the intentions of the learner were particularly important; often a desire to learn for a particular purpose can assist in overcoming many obstacles and inhibitions. Intentions also influence a learner’s approach to a situation and the ways which were chosen to process experience (Boud, Keogh, & Walker, 2013).

Living as a Blaan Learner

The Blaans occupies a hilly and mountainous area shared between Sarangani, South Cotabato, Davao del Sur, and Davao del Norte. A few rivers divided the region, and two mountain groups of volcanic origin were outstanding, namely Mount Matutum and Mount Parker on the west side of General Santos City, which contributed to the fertilization of their slopes and especially the Koronadal valley around the city of Polomolok (Gueguen, 2015).

The basic culture of Blaan was dry cultivation of a broad range of food plants including rice, supplemented by food gathering and hunting. Culture change was in an advanced stage. The Blaan language was classified in a group that included the Tiruray and T’boli, which were distinct from the Central Philippine group. The same pattern of scattered settlements existed among the group although the houses generally remained within sight of each other near swidden fields. Rice, corn, and millet were planted (National Commission for Culture and the Arts, 2019).

According to Kinoc (2020), Blaan life revolved around the family which usually was a compound consisting of more than one spouse or a home consisting of extended relatives living together. Blaans had a pronounced or defined role in the family. The man did all the heavy work while the woman did less burdensome work. The man opened and prepared the farms, the woman tended to the crops until

harvest. The man prepared the storage bins and the woman hauled the harvest for storing.

Close family ties had always been recognized as one of the core values of Blaan families and were deeply embedded in their culture; the life of the Blaan evolved around their family that usually lived within one compound, consisting of more than one spouse and extended relatives living together. To protect their property and to secure themselves from intrusions, most marriages were limited to close relatives; within this, community cousins were allowed to marry each other (De Jong, 2020).

Perspectives of children and young people in education were rarely sought, but respecting students as knowers and actors in incorporating student views was central to reforms in education that aimed to change the culture of education. Many students expressed a desire to learn more about indigenous content at school. Some were critical of the brevity and limitations of the Indigenous knowledge and curriculum perspectives taught: lack of depth, quality, the need for authenticity, and the value of such content (Wilson & Wilks, 2013).

It is already known that education is one very critical area. In spite of a net enrolment of 91.21 % in primary education, only 70.96 % have been able to complete elementary school in 2011 (NSCB, 2013). And these statistics are more dismal for IP youths. There are an estimated 5.1 million IPs under 18 years old in the Philippines, however, only around 1.2 million IP children are enrolled in elementary and high schools (Calunsod, 2013). Unfortunately, these statistics are not surprising. IP youths are considered to be one of the most vulnerable groups for living in remote areas and having “very limited access to basic services,” which include education (Cornelio & Castro, 2016).

Over 11 million indigenous people in the Philippines, many of whom live in very remote locations around the country with limited access to technology and quality education. Because of its remote location, indigenous students face several barriers to education such as having no electricity, students walking for hours to go to school, and teachers trekking down mountains just to reach these communities (Microsoft Philippines Communications Team, 2019).

Moreover, because of the distance between some communities to the schools, education becomes difficult to achieve for them. According to interviews, graduating from primary and secondary education is already a big achievement for them despite their less capacity to send children to school. There are even times when students could not attend school for the whole week due to financial difficulties. Those who are lucky are enrolled in the Alternative Learning System of the Department of Education. Those who are luckier have graduated high school and are now employed with earning enough to sustain their primary needs (Tindowen, Bassig, & Cagurangan, 2017).

Furthermore, the current structure of formal education seems to not fully satisfy and is constantly adjusting to necessarily address their immediate needs in terms of language instruction, for example, or modes of learning, especially when they decide to pursue higher education (Adonis & Couch, 2017). Another problem that some indigenous communities have encountered is the military conflict between government forces and community revolutionaries in the countryside. Reports have been documented, concerning schools being occupied by the military, exposing children to violence, and leaving them traumatized (ABS-CBN News, 2012). Although efforts have already been initiated for many years to address the inaccessibility of education among IP youths.

Despite the developments, there is still a lack of educators proficient in the language of IPs/ICCs, as the majority of Mother Tongue-based subjects cover only local dialects and languages but not actually the language of the Indigenous natives. Another problem is that the majority of subjects being taught in educational institutions require the use of English terms in the absence of an ethnic equivalent for the foreign words which are primarily English words (Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021).

Also, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, public school teachers were not conducting face-to-face classes until a vaccine has been developed. In IP areas, even cellphone and broadcast signals can be absent and few children have access to electronic gadgets or even radios and televisions. Indigenous People’s Education Office (IPsEO) and IP Education Focal Persons throughout the country have been continuously considering ways not only to address the challenge of how learning materials can be accessed but how children can be guided in using these materials. As elsewhere in the country, parents and other family members will have a major role in assisting young children. Perhaps, family members can become content sources of the learning materials. They can help make simple stories for children given their knowledge of the language. However, for IP communities the level of literacy and formal schooling in adults tends to be low, making this role more challenging (Ingle, 2021).

Although these remote tribes were slowly being forced into a modern world, they continued to struggle daily with life’s most basic essentials. They were in desperate need of quality medical care, modern farming techniques, and educational opportunities (Joshua Project, 2020).

Some studies found to be related to this present study were also reviewed. The review aimed to find more directions and insights on the procedures on how the variables of this present study may be treated.

Studies across the Cordillera region show that the most common aspiration of farming families is a college education for their children, even if they can barely afford the cost (Asian Development Bank, 2013). It is common to find farming households selling a piece of land or a precious heirloom to pay for their children’s school expenses. Consequently, expenditure for agricultural production is sacrificed. Respondents explain that a college degree for their children is their passport out of farming. This finding suggests that some

farmers in the village see the attainment of the “good life” as being outside the confines of their village. Indeed, outmigration is a common phenomenon all over the Cordillera.

In the study by Galindo, Reginio, Liguid, Sancon, and Advincula (2018) in Davao del Sur, about the Lived Experiences of the Indigenous People in Reaching Their Full Academic Potentials, the researchers revealed that the contemporary IP youth are much more empowered and are very much determined to fulfill their hopes and dreams in life despite the unending problem with IP discrimination which had caused their fears. The result of this study showed how IP youth have given high importance to education for they believe that it will serve as their freedom from long-time discrimination. It is also considered as their way out from their hardships in life and more than that, they hoped to raise their very own community and be the instrument of change as future leaders.

Similarly, Dela Cruz' (2021) phenomenological case study explored the lived experiences of four indigenous Aeta youth members who aspire to finish college education in the Philippines. Using the photo-elicitation technique of Photovoice, data were collected through focus group discussions and one-on-one interviews over a period of two years from June of 2018. Six themes emerged in the interviews: “display of resilience”, “living in two worlds”, “education is the key”, “family first”, “pride for the indigenous community”, and “inclusive and supportive environment”.

Another study titled “Lived Experiences of the Time Preceding Burnout” by Ekstedt and Fagerberg (2015) showed that the essential meaning of the phenomenon of burnout was understood as being trapped with stimulating challenges as a self-nourishing drive on one side and with responsibilities and demands on the other. According to the study, data were collected from interviews with eight people suffering from burnout and analyzed using a phenomenological study.

The study “The Lived Experiences of Professional Clinical Psychologists Who Recently Started a New Academic Career” by Du Plessis et al. (2013) stated in their study that they used a method that broadly followed the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) method laid out by Smith and Osborn—one of the key components of the study related to the inclusion of a small and relatively homogenous sample that was accessed through a method that could be described as purposeful sampling. With this in mind, the researchers gathered a group of three Clinical Psychologists who had recently started a new academic career, appointed as permanent members of staff at a large tertiary institution in South Africa.

The researchers concluded that the decision to leave a safe career path and venture forward into the unknown could be construed as either madness or wisdom. This move has threatened our identities and allowed us to move towards a place and sense of non-identity. The phenomenological analysis of their conversation yielded rich insight into the experience of becoming academics in relation to their pre-existing professional identities.

In another study by Reyes, Isip, and Dizon (2021), the researchers described the challenges and coping strategies of the Aeta in Pampanga, Philippines. The researchers concluded that the Aeta students encountered challenges in conversational English because of their belief that they have weaknesses in the English language, and poor vocabulary. The Aeta students feel the need to overcome these challenges by researching, watching people on television, and consulting the dictionary. The researchers proposed the development of a module that should be simple and include grammar, writing, reading, and vocabulary which aims to provide improvement in the skills needed by the Aeta students in conversational English.

Meanwhile, in the study conducted by Tang (2020) titled, “The Lived Experiences of People with Disabilities and their Families: Transitioning to Adulthood and the Role of Independent Facilitation”, fourteen informants were recruited through purposeful and convenience sampling. Data collection procedures consisted of background questionnaires and one-on-one semi-structured interviews which were then thematically analyzed.

Likewise, a study titled “Living with Breast Cancer: Iranian Women’s Lived Experiences” by Joolae, Joolae, Kadivar, and Hajibabae (2012) used a phenomenological approach to explore the meaning of living with breast cancer for Iranian women. The patients’ feelings and lived experiences with breast cancer were investigated using semi-structured interviews with probing questions with thirteen women between thirty-four and sixty-seven years old. According to the findings of their study, the informants explained their experiences of living with breast cancer as losing something important, lack of confidence, living with fear, emotional dizziness, and the need to be supported with the negative aspects of breast cancer and helped to explore new aspects of life as positive aspects of this event.

The researcher concluded that transitioning to adulthood for people with disabilities and their families was a “challenging yet rewarding” process. She stated that this study was novel in its inclusion of EAD’s voices in formal research. Although many hardships were discussed, positive aspects of the journeys into adulthood emerged which showed the role of independent facilitation, a concept that had not been formally studied previously.

In conclusion, most of the research about lived experiences used a phenomenological approach in conducting their studies. Moreover, based on the studies mentioned above, analyzing the lived experiences of certain groups and communities could provide us with authentic and deep information about their feelings and struggles. With this, we could learn from their stories and help find a solution to their problems and paved the way for their voices to be heard by everyone.

Methodology

Research Design

This is a descriptive phenomenological study that aimed to explore and describe the experiences and narratives of Blaan Learners at Lanao Kapanglao Integrated School. It focuses on understanding the essence of these narratives from the perspective of the participants themselves, without imposing preconceived theories or frameworks. In this study, the researcher sought to uncover the underlying structures, patterns, and meanings inherent in the phenomena being studied, allowing for a rich and detailed exploration of human consciousness and perception (Creswell & Poth, 2016). This approach often involves in-depth interviews, participant observations, and the systematic analysis of textual data to uncover the essential qualities and characteristics of the lived experiences and narratives of the Blaan Learners.

Participants

In phenomenology, lived experience was defined as the encounters in everyday experience, pre-reflectively taken for granted as reality rather than as something perceived or represented (Oxford University Press, 2020). I gathered the narratives of the lived experiences of purposively selected Blaan students from Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School.

The participants of this study were the five (5) learners from Lanao Kapanglao Elementary school. They had strong views about education as they were active in school. The informants were Blaan learners who were honor students in the school. The participants were coded as “BL 1”, “BL 2”, “BL 3”, “BL 4”, and “BL 5” where “BL” stands for “Blaan Learner”.

Instruments

The Descriptive Phenomenology design employed in this study, following Matua and Van der Wal's (2015) recommendations, underscores the importance of providing detailed descriptions of individuals' experiences without imposing interpretation. Through one-on-one interviews with participants, I aimed to delve into the lived experiences of Blaan learners, using a semi-structured interview guide that underwent validation by experts in the field. In phenomenology, lived experience encompasses the encounters individuals have in their everyday lives, which they accept as reality without conscious reflection or interpretation (Oxford University Press, 2020). By collecting narratives of lived experiences from purposively selected Blaan students at Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School, we sought to capture the richness and depth of their experiences within their cultural context.

Procedure

In piloting the study, I obtained permission from the School Head of Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School to conduct my research. Upon approval, I collaborated with the advisers to select five active Blaan learners who were part of the honor roll, gathering their names and addresses for further contact. This facilitated one-on-one interviews with the participants. Adhering to health and safety protocols, I wore a face mask and shield, and provided additional protective gear to the informants. Five participants were interviewed to elucidate the lived experiences of Blaan learners. Before the interviews commenced, I distributed consent forms to the learners, explaining the study's purpose, procedures, confidentiality agreements, and potential benefits. I also obtained consent from the parents of the participants.

Participants selected the interview site where they felt most comfortable sharing their stories. I recommended a secluded location to minimize distractions and ensure their focus. Before commencing the interviews, I sanitized the area and our hands with alcohol spray. I verbally reviewed the consent forms with each participant, ensuring their comprehension of the study's objectives and the interview process.

Unstructured interviews were conducted, allowing participants to express themselves freely. According to Bhasin (2019), such interviews provide participants with the opportunity to convey their perspectives more authentically, fostering deeper insights into their experiences. Questions were formulated as guiding prompts, but the interviewees were encouraged to share their stories organically, without strict adherence to a predetermined set of questions. Bisaya/Cebuano was used as the primary language of communication during the interviews. All sessions were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and translated into English and Filipino for analysis. Interviews lasted between thirty minutes to one hour, with a maximum duration of one hour to minimize prolonged direct contact with the participants.

Data Analysis

To analyze the gathered data, I adopted a mixed approach combining thematic analysis and an inductive approach. As per Gabriel (2013), the inductive approach utilized research questions to focus the study's scope, while thematic analysis enabled a close examination of the data to identify recurring themes, topics, ideas, and patterns of meaning. This methodological blend provided a straightforward means of deriving findings in this study. As for my recorded audios, I have to transcribe each of the responses before analyzing their themes.

Additionally, I employed techniques outlined by Dudovskiy (2013), which include scanning for common words and phrases used by the participants, comparing interview findings with the literature review, and exploring aspects that were not addressed by the

participants, considering them as core ideas for the major themes selected.

Following data analysis, I synthesized the findings by aligning them with the research questions. Guided by Jerome Bruner's narrative construction theory, as articulated by Hein (2012), which posits that knowledge is constructed by the knower rather than existing independently, the conclusions, insights, and lessons drawn from the narratives of Indigenous learners were shaped by my own experiences and evolving understanding throughout the research process.

Ethical Considerations

I ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College because it helped me avoid engaging in practices which may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those whom I sought to do research with.

Informed Consent. I sought my informants' consent to avoid any offense or discomfort regarding the disclosure of the data coming from them. The purpose of the study, its intentions and scope, their right to withdraw their participation during the collection of data if they notice some discrepancies or any violation of their rights was explained to them. The confidentiality of the informants was considered. Since they are the primary source of data, the results of this study were treated properly to maintain confidentiality and to avoid offenses against the participants. Their identity was kept protected.

Voluntary Participation. There was no force involved in the conduct of this study. The informants' participation was voluntary and they were informed beforehand that they may withdraw or discontinue taking part in the study. I ensured that the essential implications for consent protocols were addressed, which means that informants must be thoroughly informed about the procedures and hazards associated with the study.

Cultural Sensitivity. Throughout the conduct of my study, it was an ethical imperative for me to endure cultural sensitivity in all areas or aspects of my research and maintain the commitment to not harm culture. Furthermore, I was careful on issues such as exploitation, community damage, and inaccurate findings especially when it comes to age, dialectical oppositions/discriminations, cultural practices, customs, traditions, beliefs, religion, and even academic, economic, and social status.

Gender Sensitivity. I took all appropriate measures to eliminate gender discrimination and ensured the equal rights of men and women. The informants are entitled to their rights without distinction of any kind of gender discrimination.

Data Privacy. I ensured that my informants' privacy was protected. In addition, adequate confidentiality of the research data was maintained. Their responses, as well as the anonymity of individuals and organizations taking part in the research was protected. I also assured them that their trust and confidence in me remain.

Components to be assessed. I focused mainly on the narratives of the five Blaan learners during their one-on-one interview with me. Themes and core ideas were formulated based on their statements. Here, only those that were relevant, appropriate, and within the study's scope were presented. Moreover, I ensured that only those which were properly documented were included.

Health Safety Protocols. Since my study requires a face-to-face interview with the informants, I maintained the required physical distance, wearing a face mask, and a face shield. Also, I sanitized the area where the interview was conducted and used alcohol and hand sanitizer frequently. These protocols were also applied by the informants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of analyzing the data from interviews with the five participants. The chapter starts with a brief description of the five participants while using codes to keep their personal information confidential. The data and themes were evaluated and presented in this section.

The Participants

The participants of this study were five (5) Grade 5 Blaan learners who were enrolled in Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School. The informants were coded as "BL 1", "BL 2", "BL 3", "BL 4", and "BL 5" where "BL" stands for "Blaan Learner". This section focuses on the brief introduction of the key informants of this study. The following paragraphs were taken from the interviews.

"BL 1" is the eighth of the ten children in their family. According to her, five of her siblings are already married. Her parents are both farmers however recently, her mother could not work anymore because of a respiratory disease. Due to this situation, she cooks breakfast for her family every day and takes care of her sick mother.

"BL 2" is the youngest of the five children. All of her siblings were already married and have built their own family. She mentioned that her mother is a farmer and his father died recently.

"BL 3" is the second of the five children born in their family. According to him, only three of them were blood-related. He said that his father had a partner and two children before meeting his mother. Unfortunately, two years ago, his father died. BL 3 mentioned that his mother lives in another place and has now a child and a new partner. As the interview progressed, he revealed that he is living with his grandparents along with his other siblings.

“BL 4” was the fourth to be interviewed. She is a part of a larger family. She is the 10th of the 11 children born in their family. As the interview progressed, she revealed that she also has five siblings from her father’s side, making them 16 children in total. It appeared that her father had children with another woman. She mentioned that her mother was her father’s first partner. As the interview continued, she said most of her brothers and sisters embarked in early marriage and left home. She is currently living with her mother and father along with her younger sister.

“BL 5” was the last informant to be interviewed. He is ten (10) years old and the youngest of the five children in their family. He stated that all of his siblings prioritize education and are committed to completing their studies including him.

The Narratives of Blaans Learners on their Life as a Learner and a Child

Given that the Indigenous community is continuously facing challenges, there are added difficulties for young indigenous learners. Since they are still children, their social, physical, and environmental surroundings are important as they are more vulnerable to risks. The Blaans learners detailed their experiences and difficulties even at a young age. During the interview of this study, three main themes emerged, that is “environmental threats”, “social distress”, and “physical stress”.

Table 1. *The Narratives of Blaans Learners on their Life as a Learner and a Child*

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Environmental Threats	Navigating dangerous terrains	General
	Dealing with the presence of wild animals	General
Social Distress	Becoming independent at a young age	General
	Being in a large family	General
Physical Stress	Being physically exhausted from long walks	General
	Experiencing pangs of hunger	General

Environmental Threats

The theme “environmental threats” to Blaans learners was significantly highlighted during the interview. It was found that the students live in sitios or barangays adjacent to the school and have to pass through dangerous roads going to school. They are exposed to unpaved roads that can erode easily, especially during rainy seasons, and unmaintained surroundings which may be home to wild animals and are highly dangerous to young students.

Navigating Dangerous Terrains. The matter of dangerous routes to school was discussed among the five informants. The question of their routes to and from the school was asked directly. When the informants were asked how the road from their homes going to school is, they all answered that the road is very slippery and muddy.

“Grabe kaayo ang lapok Sir... Danlog kaayo sir” (It [the route] is very muddy, Sir... (It’s very slippery sir)- BL 1

“Kanang lapok Sir nya danlog... Okay ra Sir pero lapok kaayo. Nadugayan mi ganina kay danlog kaayo...” (It’s [the route] muddy and slippery, Sir. It was okay Sir but very muddy. It took us [BL 2 and her sibling] long to arrive because it [the road] was slippery...) - BL 2

“Danlog kaayo, daghan kaayog lapok...” (It is very slippery and muddy) – BL 3

“Maayo sir, lapok kayo...” (Good sir, but very muddy) – BL 4

“Lapok sir. Kanang pag mag ulan sir lapok kaayo...” (It’s [the route] muddy sir. It’s [the route] very muddy when it rains.)- BL 5

Aside from the slippery and muddy roads, “BL 3” also added that there are a lot of fallen big trees and branches along the way which is very dangerous for the students.

“Mga kahoy... Nga tumba...” (Lots of trees... Fallen trees) – BL 3

Education is the most effective method to prevent or at least minimize many environmental problems before they appear. Unfortunately, geographical education is not always able to meet the demands of sustainability. There are many obstacles to teachers being unable to implement sufficient knowledge and skills (Sinan, Usak, & Sinan, 2022).

Dealing with the Presence of Wild Animals. These unpaved and unmaintained roads also become a habitat for wild animals. When I asked “BL 2” about her journey from home to school, she said that many students and parents were complaining about the route as it was overgrown with bushes and they were afraid of snake encounters.

“Kanang nagreklamo ang mga estudyante dira...Bagnet kaayo ang dalan sir...Nagreklamo gani ang mga ginikanan ug estudyante basi naay mga bitin daw kay libon na kaayo dira...” (The students are complaining. The route is overgrown with bushes Sir. The parents and students are even complaining that there might be snakes as it [the route] looks like a jungle...) – BL 2

“BL 3” and “BL 5” also echoed a response similar to “BL 2” when asked about the route he takes when going to school. They said

that they had often encountered snakes along the way.

“*Bagnet kaayo sir...*” (*Grasses are really tall sir*) – BL 3

“*Naay bitin Sir...*” (*There’s a snake Sir.*) – BL 5

“*Ginalabayan namo ug bato sir...Kadaghan nami kasugat*

Sir.” (*We throw rocks at it [snake] Sir...We often encounter*

The informants are raising an important issue on the topic of their journey to school. As they have mentioned during the interview, I can say that the route they take is extremely dangerous for school children. They also mentioned frequent snake encounters because of overgrown bushes on the road. Aside from that, the route is muddy and slippery, especially on rainy days. It appears that the informants have been struggling with this problem and their parents have also raised complaints regarding this matter.

A study by Su, Jerrett, McConnell, Berhane, Dunton, Shankardass, and Wolch (2013) revealed that children from low-income communities faced greater environmental and safety concerns yet were more pertinent to walk to school. Since the less advantaged communities had higher rates of children walking to school, attention to safety is particularly important so those children are not injured on their way to school. Placing schools in residential areas and developing safe routes and social marketing strategies will shorten the distance traveled and reduce safety concerns.

Social Distress

Aside from the dangers that their environment brings, the Balaan learners also face social stress brought about by being in a large family with low income which automatically forces them to be independent even at a young age and be burdened by household chores instead of focusing only on their studies.

Becoming Independent at a Young Age. Most of the informants knew the household chores as they were often tasked by their parents, guardians or family members. Some of them had to do the tasks by themselves because those were important life skills that they needed to learn. During the interview, BL 1 stated that she does household chores such as sweeping the floor and washing dishes. She also said that after coming back from school, she immediately washed her clothes. Meanwhile, BL 5 said that when there is no class, he helps his father remove weeds.

“*Magluto ug kan on sir...Manilhig ko sa amuang balay nya maghugas ug plato...Pag uli nako gikan sa skwelahan, manglaba ko sa akong bulingon sir...*” (*I cook rice Sir... I sweep the floor and wash dishes at home... After school, I wash my clothes, Sir.*)- BL 1

“*Manglampas sir...kauban nako akong papa sir*” (*Removing weeds sir... Along with my father, Sir.*)- BL 5 those [snakes] Sir.) – BL 5

Family structure in childhood and adolescence may affect subjective aging because it is linked to responsibilities in the family as well as the timing of entry into adult roles. Children in single-parent homes grew up faster because they often became “junior partners” in household management (Johnson & Mollborn, 2019). In an interview with BL 3, he said that he gathered wood and water when there were no classes. However, he said that the location of the water pump station was very far and he had to carry two gallons of water.

“*Daghan sir. Magkuha ko ug sugnod, magkabo ug tubig...Layo kayo sir...Tag duha [kagallon] akong ginabitbit...*” (*There’s a lot to do, Sir. I gather woods and water...It’s [location of the water pump station] very far, Sir I usually carry two gallons [of water]*)- BL 3

On the other hand, BL 2 shared that she is now the one doing the household chores and preparing her lunchbox as her mother could not do those anymore. She revealed that her mother got injured.

“*Magluto ug kan on nya mamahaw nya iandam ang balon sa recess...Dili ka andam akong mama kay naay sakit akong mama sir...Manglimpyo, manghugas nya mangguna sa simbahan...Kung walay klase sir, manarbaha mi nya magtabang sa akong ate ug harbis...*” (*I cook rice, eat my breakfast, and prepare my lunchbox for recess... My mother can’t help me prepare as she is injured, Sir... Cleaning, washing dishes, and chopping out the weeds around our church...If there’s no class, we work at our farm and help my sister in harvesting.*)- BL 2

I also asked BL 2 what happened to her mother. She said that her mother recently got into a minor accident and was still recovering.

“*Wala pa [naulian] sir...Nadagma man daw to Sir pauli. Nya paghilot sa silingan namo sa iyaha kay kanang kuan daw napiang daw sya...*” (*Not yet [recovered] sir...According to my mother, she stumbled on her way home. Our neighbor massaged her and told us [a part of her body] was dislocated.*)- BL 2

Like other informants, I also asked BL 4 what she usually does at home during school days and weekends. It seemed that BL 4 did her best to help her stepmother do household chores. She mentioned how her mother did the chores when there were classes. Even though she was not a biological daughter, her stepmother looked after her especially during school days.

“*Maglubo sa mais sir...Magkabo sir...Magluto ug kan-on sir, maghugas ug plato pagkatapos wala na...Kung nay klase, walay trabaho sir kay si mama man ga atiman sa balay...Pag uli gikan sa skwelahan sir, kung walay tubig sa balay mangabo ko...*” (*Removing corn*

kernels from cob sir Gathering water sir... Cooking rice Sir, washing dishes and after that my work is done. If there are classes, I don't work because my mother does the chores. After school, I gather water if there's none left at home.)- BL 4

Recent ethnographic accounts of poor inner-city youth from economically pressed families suggested that children and teenagers age into adulthood very quickly in these settings. Family disruption and poverty, along with other conditions of deprivation or stress like feeling unsafe in daily life, represented key hardships implicated in subjective aging during the early life course (Settersen, Ottusch, & Schneider, 2015).

Being in a Large Family. The theme formulated from the narratives of Grade 5 Blaen learners was "Being in a Large Family". Here, the informants stated the number of children in their family as well as the occupation of their parents. All of the informants were part of a family that has five children and more. Also, most of them have half-siblings as a result of their parents' remarriage.

BL 1 stated that there were ten children born in their family. She was the eighth of the ten children. She mentioned that her mother could not work anymore because of a respiratory disease. Meanwhile, BL 5 shared that there were five children in the family and their eldest was in Grade 9.

"Pulo mi sir. Lima ka babae, lima ka lalaki...Ika-walo ko sir... Lima ang minyo sa amua sir..." (We are ten, sir. Five girls and five boys...I'm the eighth [of the ten children] sir... Five are married sir.)- BL 1

"Lima mi sir. Kamanghuran ko sir. 3 ka babae, 2 ka lalaki... Wala ko kabalo sa pangalan sa akong ate sir. Grade 9 pa sya sir..." (There are five [children], sir. I'm the youngest, sir. 3 girls and 2 boys...I don't know the name of my eldest sister, sir. She's in Grade 9.)- BL 5

A study of poor, rural communities in Mexico found that family size predicts anxiety in adolescents and a related study of urban-slum children in India found a correlation between family size and psychiatric disorders. However, these results may reflect the stress and problems related to raising many children with limited resources (Patil, Nagaonkar, Shah & Bhat, 2013).

BL 2 had four siblings and she was the youngest of the five children. She stated that all of her siblings were already married. During the interview, she also revealed that her father died last year. BL 2's mother was a farmer and because of the death of her father, her mother is the only one providing their basic needs.

"Lima mi sir. Bunso ko...Minyo na sila [mga igsuon] tanan sir. Ang ate nako bag-o lang sya naminyo...Mag-uuma akong mama sir.... Wala nakoy papa sir. Patay na. Tung May 4, 2021. Didto sya namatay sa Malapatan... Nasakit lang gud sir..." (We are five, sir. I'm the youngest...They [siblings] are all married, sir. My sister got married recently... My mother is a farmer sir...I don't have a father, sir. He died last 4th of May 2021. He died there at Malapatan...He was sick, sir.)- BL 2

Meanwhile, BL 3 has three biological siblings and two half-siblings. It appeared that his father had two partners. He mentioned that his mother was the second partner.

*"Lima mi sir...Ika duha ko sir...6 pa ang kamanghuran sir. Wala pa sya nagskwela ug kinder...Duha man asawa sa akong papa sir. Tulo mi mag igsuon sa mama. Duha ako igsuon sa isa nako ka mama...Ang akoang mama ulahi. Mama ni ***** mao ang una..." (We are five sir...I'm the second...Our youngest is 6 years old sir. She's currently not attending Kindergarten, sir... My father has actually two partners, sir. Three of us have the same mother while the remaining two share the same mother...My mother was the second [partner]. *****'s mother was the first.)- BL 3*

BL 3 added that his mother found a new partner after the death of his father. He said that her mother now has a child with her new partner and is currently living with him. He also stated that he is now living with his grandparents along with his siblings.

"Pero namatay akong papa nya nanguha na sya ug asawa didto sa Maligo...Dugay na namatay sir. Katong June 2020... Naa nay laing bana akong mama sir. Taga Maligo tung sundalo. Naa na silay anak isa...Naa na sya didto sa Maligo. Didto gud dapit sa Polomolok...Kauban nako akong isa ka mama. Tapos pag minyo usab ni mamang, didto napud sya sa ila lolo. Dira napud ko sa akong isa ka lolo...Sa ila lola ug lolo ko nagpuyo... Kauban nako sila kuya..." (But my father died and she found a partner in Maligo...He [his father] died a long time ago sir. Last June 2020...My mother has now a new partner sir. Her partner was from Maligo and was a soldier. They have one child...She's [his biological mother] now residing in Maligo. Near in Polomolok...I livednwith my second mom [for a short time]. But when my second mom remarried, she lived with my grandparents [his second mother's parents]. I'm living now with my other grandparents [his father's parents]...I'm with my siblings.)- BL 3

On the other hand, BL 4 revealed that there were a total of sixteen (16) children born in their family, however three (3) of her siblings died. Like BL 3, her father had two partners. BL 4 also mentioned that both her parents did not have a job.

"11 mi sir pero namatay ang tulo...Ika 10 ko sir...Duha ang asawa sa akong papa sir. Anak ko sa unang asawa sir... 11 mi mag igsuon sa inahan sir...Lima sa ikaduhang asawa ni papa sir...Walay trabaho akong papa sir. Maglampas lang sya sir...Wala pud trabaho akong mama... Wala ko kabalo kung unsa ginabuhat didto sa akong isa ka mama sir... Duha ra mi dili minyo sir..." (We are eleven sir but three died...I'm the 10th sir...My father has two partners sir. I'm a child of the first partner sir... Eleven of us are pure biologically related...Meanwhile, the other five share the same mother...My father has no occupation sir...He only removes weeds,

sir...My mother has no occupation too sir...I don't know about the job of my other mother sir... Only two of us [BL 4 and her sibling] are not married, sir.)- BL 4

Among indigenous people in South Central Mindanao, the phenomenon of early marriage had been reported to be common. The socio-political impact of early marriage, seen from the perspectives of human rights, was also among the least tackled in the few studies of early marriage among Indigenous people in Mindanao (Francisco, Pauya, & Millenes, 2021).

Moreover, a study conducted in the regions of the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) and CARAGA regarding the sexual and reproductive health revealed that participants across both regions shared that adolescent boys and girls who were unmarried and sexually active were considered immoral and often face stigma and social disapproval. Aside from that, participants shared that it was common and expected for couples to have large family sizes regardless of socio-economic status, age of women and health consequences, and this exerted a strong influence on couples choosing to have children soon after getting married (Valerio & Butt, 2020).

Physical Stress

The theme of Physical Stress has also emerged from the interview of the Blaan learners. Given that they belong in a low-income community, some necessary amenities are not convenient for them such as water sources and food availability. It was stated they have to walk long distances and carry heavy weights to collect water for daily chores. They also have to walk long distances going to school from their houses with an empty stomach which is physically draining especially for the young students.

Being Physically Exhausted from Long Walks. One of the aspects that adds to the physical stress of the learners is physical exhaustion from these long walks. While I was asking a question related to his daily routine, “BL 3” mentioned that he walks a very long route to get water. The informant stated that the distance from his house to the water pump is approximately 600 meters. He has to walk that distance to get two gallons of water.

“Layo kaayo sir... Diri ug Lanao” (From afar sir... Here to Lanao) – BL 3

According to Bruno and Loris (2021), fatigue is a subjective feeling and its ill effects are frequently seen in many ways, such as task performance decrement, cognitive impairment, and emotional disturbance. In school children, fatigue can lead to a decline in school performance, negative health outcomes, and refusal to attend to school

The rest of the informants have also mentioned the location of their homes which are located in purok and sitios outside where the school is, and have to walk approximately an hour or more in those dangerous terrains just to get to school. Experiencing Pangs of Hunger. Another core idea found that adds to the physical stress of the Blaan learners is hunger. When I asked all the informants at the beginning of the interview if they had breakfast before going to school, “BL 2” and “BL 4” have stated that they went to school with an empty stomach because there is no food at home.

“Wala pa sir... Kay Walay sud-an sir” (Not yet sir... We don't have food) – BL 2

“Wala sir... Wala sir kay walay sud-an... Mangayo kog sud-an unya kay Lakiya” (No sir... Because we don't have food... I'll just ask from Lakiya) – BL 4

“BL 4” has also added that this usually happens more often. They would go to school without a proper meal. She stated that she sometimes just brings corn rice and just asks for a viand from her classmates.

“Usahay naay sud-an usahay wala” (Sometimes there isn't) – BL 4

This situation is also the same in the findings of the study by Nedal and Alcoriza (2018). The study revealed the monthly income of the family of the indigenous students. The monthly income of 80% of the respondents is P1000 and above, followed by P801-P1000 (12.5%), P500-P800 (2.5%), and 5% of the respondents earn only P500 and below. Because of poverty, most of the students enrolled in Lanao Elementary School eat their meals once a day. They are collecting fruits and wild crops while on their way to school, that's why they are sometimes late for their class.

Moreover, the study also revealed that the distance from their homes to the school is one of the challenges that the indigenous learners face wherein they have to walk 1-2 hours to reach the school from their sitios.

The Narratives of Blaan Learners on their Goals and Aspirations

Aside from the above-mentioned environmental and social difficulties that the young Blaan learners experience, the theme of High Academic Motivation also emerged during the interview.

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>
High Academic Motivation	Having a clear ambition	General
	Display of resilience	General

High Academic Motivation

During the interview, the Blaen Learners also expressed high motivation and eagerness when it comes to their studies. Amidst the above-mentioned difficulties that they encounter, they still showed an ambition to finish their studies. The core ideas found in this theme were “having a clear ambition” and “display of resilience.”

Having a Clear Ambition. The concept of having a clear ambition turned up when the Blaen Learners were asked directly if they have an ambition in life and what they want to become in the future. The informants responded that they all want to be a teacher and this ambition is motivated by their desire to either help their families or give back to the children of the indigenous community.

“Mag maestra sir... Para makatabang ko saakong pamilya inig makatrabaho” (To be a teacher sir... So, I can help my family when I have a job)- BL 1

“Teacher sir... Kay para matabang nako akong pamilya sir” (Teacher sir... So, I can help my family)- BL 4

This theme is found in the results of the study by Galindo, et al., (2018) wherein the researchers revealed that the contemporary indigenous youth are much more empowered and are very much determined to fulfill their hopes and dreams in life despite the unending problem in the indigenous community.

Both “BL 1” and “BL 4” answered that they want to become teachers someday because they want to help their families with their living situations.

“Mag maestra sir... Para makatabang ko saakong pamilya inig makatrabaho” (To be a teacher sir... So, I can help my family when I have a job)- BL 1

“Teacher sir... Kay para matabang nako akong pamilya sir” (Teacher sir... So, I can help my family)- BL 4

Meanwhile, both “BL 2” and “BL 3” answered that they also want to become teachers in the future in the hopes of helping other children also like what their role model teachers are showing them. While “BL 1” added that aside from being a teacher, she also dreams to be a policewoman someday with the same motivation of helping other people.

“Teacher... Para makatabang pud sa uban sir... Kanangmutabang sa uban, mutudlo sa mga bata” (Teacher... So, I can help others sir... They help others and teach children sir)- BL 2

“Maging maestro sir... Kay mutudlo silag bata para ang bata naay matun-an” (Be a teacher sir... Because they teach children so we can learn)- BL 3

“Kung dili ko magmaestra sir, magpulis ko... Para makatabang ko sa mga tao sir” (If not a teacher, I want to be a policewoman... So, I can help people sir)- BL 1

When they were asked about their ambition, the informants directly answered what their dreams are which emphasized that they have a clear ambition despite being aware of the difficulties in their education.

Additionally, studies across the Cordillera region revealed that the most common aspiration of farming families is a college education for their children, even if they can barely afford the cost (Nandi, Pratheepa, Nedumaran, Rao, & Raj, 2021). This is why it is common to find farming households selling a piece of land or a precious heirloom to support their children’s education. The respondents explained that a college degree for their children is their passport out of farming.

Display of Resilience. The other core idea that emerged from this theme is their display of resilience. All of the informants are aware of and have mentioned the difficulties that they encounter in going to school, yet they still displayed their desire to study.

At the beginning of the interview, some of the informants stated that they have not eaten breakfast yet before going to school that day and there are a lot of times in the past also that they do not eat before going to school because they have no food at home. Despite that, they chose to go to school with an empty stomach and treated this situation as normal.

“Wala pa sir... Walay sud-an sir” (Not yet sir... We don't have food)- BL 2

“Wala sir... Wala sir kay walay sud-an... Nagbalon ko sir... Mangayo ra kog sud-an unya kay Lakiya” (No sir... Because there's no viand... Yes sir, I brought lunch... I'll just ask viand from Lakiya)- BL 3

“Usahay naay sud-an usahay wala” (Sometimes we have food, other times there isn't)- BL 4

This theme is also present in the findings of Dela Cruz’ (2021) phenomenological case study that explored the lived experiences of indigenous Aeta youth members who aspire to finish college education in the Philippines. Six themes emerged in the interviews: “display of resilience”, “living in two worlds”, “education is the key”, “family first”, “pride for the indigenous community”, and “inclusive and supportive environment”.

When I asked them how they study or do their assignments during nighttime at home, “BL 3” and “BL 4” have stated their struggle

with having a battery-operated flashlight as the only light source at home while they study.

“Mag answer ko kanang gabie... Ispot... Wala miy solar” (I do it at night... Flashlight... We don’t have solar light)- BL 3

“Ako sir... O sir, Ispot... O sir. Ispot ray gamit maghimog assignment” (Me sir... Yes sir, flashlight... Yes sir, we use a flashlight only)- BL 4

Regardless of this struggle, they still choose to continue studying and even initiate asking for help when they do not understand their lesson or assignments.

Lastly, this result is also supported by Ancheta et al., (2017). Their study revealed that indigenous people are firm in finding ways that they will live. They are seen to be industrious people who will not waste time inside their houses, instead, they are firm in finding means to survive every single day.

Conclusions

All of the informants have detailed their experiences as Blaan learners during the interview. Walking on a dangerous route from home to school was the first problem for these students as most of them are residing in mountain areas. Muddy and slippery roads along school routes were also reported by the informants, as well as the presence of wild animals such as snakes. As a teacher at Lanao Kapanglao Elementary School, I could feel their struggles as I had also experienced the muddy road on my way to school. This kind of route is very challenging for adults or teachers, so it is certainly much more difficult for these young learners.

Furthermore, at the age of ten, the informants already know a lot about household chores. They were trained to be independent to assist their parents in their daily lives. These children developed mature thinking because they often see the hardships of their parents. Aside from that, some of them were left by their parents and were in the care of their guardians and grandparents. Their parents’ remarriage may also contribute to their independence. Having a lot of siblings, their parents had no time to look after each one of them. Also, their older siblings embarked on early marriage and left home. Hence, they had no one to rely on but only themselves.

Lastly, the young learners also suffer from physical exhaustion with these household chores and having to walk long distances to collect water and to go to school. And since they belong to a low-income community, most of the time, they do not eat three meals per day and just go to school with an empty stomach. This might not be an ideal situation for a child, but it is considered normal for most of them.

However, despite these difficulties experienced by the informants, they are still eager to go to school and learn. Most of them dream of becoming a professional someday and one informant even shared that she dreamed of helping other people.

There were a number of implications for educational practice that may be gleaned from the current study of the narratives of Blaan learners. An essential theme that was formulated from the informants’ narratives was the environmental threats to students. Education stakeholders should be aware of this issue as the students’ safety is as important as learning. Providing aid for this, especially for those learners who live very far from school should be a top priority.

Other important findings in this study were the social and physical stress of the informants. Since most of them belong to large families, there is a big chance that they are having difficulty providing for their needs in school. Education stakeholders may further their efforts to provide learning materials for the Indigenous learners that they may also use at home such as textbooks, storybooks, radio programs, or digital learning resources.

Another important implication of my study derived from the academic and personal ambitions of the informants. After analyzing their narratives, I found out that they have clear ambitions to achieve great things in life and save their family from poverty. They look up to their teachers as their role models and I believe that teachers have great responsibilities to these learners. Accordingly, this study suggests that our education system may strive harder to provide for the educational needs of the indigent community.

This study, being of a qualitative and descriptive phenomenological nature, raises a number of opportunities for future research. More research is necessary to polish and further explain the results of this study.

First, while this study draws lessons on the narratives of Blaan learners, future research may be conducted on different Indigenous groups and not only limited to Blaan learners. It may be interesting to explore a larger scope of Indigenous groups and gain more insights into the lived experiences of Indigenous people. My study may thus be extended in search of other research methods and research designs. A second area for future research will be a study involving the Indigenous teachers as it may contribute to understanding the needs of Indigenous communities and improve the education system for IP learners.

Finally, this study may also be extended to the academic professionals who are part of Indigenous groups. I have a strong belief that many lessons can be drawn from their struggles and achievements in life. Further research may elaborate on this point that may provide valuable information to the education stakeholders, the Local Government Unit (LGU), teachers, learners, and the community.

The following recommendations were given based on the results of the study:

First, since the route is often muddy and slippery, the local government unit (LGU) may place safe road designs along school routes to encourage safety perception. Also, overgrown bushes along the road may be cut to prevent snake encounters. Second, law enforcement such as safety and crime prevention may be strengthened within the school zone to enhance safety among students and teachers as well.

Third, since most of the Blaan learners go to school alone, their parents and guardians may contribute to cleaning and maintaining these roads to be safe and free from wild animals. Local officials may also improve the walking conditions around the school to guarantee the safety of the learners.

Fourth, education stakeholders may want to consider and evaluate the concept of having boarding homes in the school community to accommodate these learners from far-flung areas that need to travel for a number of hours on a dangerous route to school. Also, the education stakeholders may organize a sponsorship program to augment the schooling of IP learners and lastly, regular counseling may be conducted for Blaan learners to counsel them on the effects of embarking on early marriage and those learners whose parents have remarried.

The present study on the lessons from narratives of Blaan learners was one of the few researches about the lived experiences of Indigenous learners in the Philippines. The study helped me fill the void in research on the Indigenous learner and contributed to understanding the culture of our brothers and sisters from Indigenous communities. One of the most important findings I discovered in this study was the environmental threats experienced by all of the informants. Distance from home to school is very crucial as it could affect the academic performance of the learners, especially in schools located in mountain areas. Learners had to walk for miles and struggle with the muddy and slippery road every day.

Meanwhile, as I was talking with the informants, the topic of the family emerged in their narratives. Most of the informants had large families and half-siblings due to the remarriage of their parents. The informants' siblings also married early and left home hence making them rely on themselves.

Upon hearing the narratives of the informants, I was overwhelmed with sadness and at the same time, I was proud and inspired by their courageous views on life. Although I worked hard not to be affected by any emotions to avoid having a biased result, I could not deny that an unexplainable feeling was tugging at my heart.

It was not an easy journey planning and conducting this study. However, despite the long and difficult route of the interview location, I was satisfied by the lessons I have drawn from the narratives of my informants. I learned important information and I can use it to share it with my readers, especially future researchers.

Lastly, findings from the present study may help inform the stakeholders, especially teachers who had Indigenous learners in their class about their struggles and make them feel well-adjusted in school. It is my hope that with this study, other researchers may feel encouraged to explore more about the lived experiences of Indigenous learners in order to gain more knowledge about their challenges and aspirations.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Elbert G. Pogado, MAEd, LPT

Lanao Kapanglao Integrated School – Philippines

Lilibeth R. Bagtas, PhD, LPT

Holy Trinity College – Philippines